

FULLY ISOTROPIC LAMINATES MADE OF (0°, +45°, -45°, 90°) LAYERS WITH UP TO 24 PLYS

J. Lee^{1*}, J. Kim¹, M. Park¹

¹ Aeronautics R&D Head Office, Korea Aerospace Research Institute, Daejeon, Korea,

* twinbee@kari.re.kr

Keywords: *composite, laminate, fully isotropic, fiber orientation, stiffness*

1 Introduction

Fibrous composites are usually constructed with multiple orthotropic layers in which the reinforcing fibers are aligned in pre-determined orientations. In most field applications with single material type, the thickness of each layer is usually an integer-multiple of the unit ply thickness. Even though the laminate stiffness components can be tailored by combining and adjusting the fiber orientation in each layer, it is not a trivial matter to find fully isotropic stacking sequences for relatively thin laminates.

The conditions for fully orthotropic laminates (FOL's), $A_{16}=A_{26}=0$, $D_{16}=D_{26}=0$ and $B_{ij}=0$, must be satisfied to obtain fully isotropic laminates (FIL's). It is also self-evident that the contribution of each fiber orientation must be kept identical to make the entire laminate fully isotropic.

In other words, the entire laminate stiffness components must be invariant with respect to the in-plane tensor transformation. For FIL's, the following relationships must be additionally satisfied.

$$A_{11} = A_{22}, \quad (1a)$$

$$A_{66} = (A_{11} - A_{12})/2, \quad (1b)$$

$$D_{ij} = A_{ij} H^2/12 \quad (2)$$

where H is the entire laminate thickness.

Caprino and Visconti [1] presented a particular class of anti-symmetric angle-ply laminates with $B_{ij}=D_{16}=D_{26}=0$. They utilized the fact that $B_{ij}=0$ for any symmetric laminate, and $A_{16}=A_{26}=0$ for any balanced laminate, and $D_{16}=D_{26}=B_{ij}=0$ for any anti-symmetric laminate. They showed that the simplest laminate is the anti-symmetric angle-ply laminate with 8 plies, $[(\pm\theta)_S/(\mp\theta)_S]$, in which all coupling terms, A_{16} , A_{26} , B_{ij} , D_{16} , and D_{26} are rigorously zero.

Gunnink [2] presented a simple comment on the result of Caprino and Visconti [1], which states "if laminate B is anti-symmetric with respect to laminate A and if laminate A as well as B is

balanced, then A_{16} , A_{26} , B_{ij} , D_{16} , and D_{26} of the entire laminate AB become rigorously zero."

Lee et al. [3] presented an analytical method to obtain fully orthotropic laminates (FOL's) with anti-symmetric stacking sequences. In their study, Pythagorean theorem and Pascal's number triangle are found to be closely related to the analytical stacking sequences sufficient to guarantee FOL's.

Vannucci and Verchery [4] proposed some new kinds of fully isotropic laminates (FIL's) obtained by the so-called polar method. They found five independent solutions for the 18 ply-laminates, one independent solution for the 24-ply laminates, 219 solutions for the 27-ply laminates, and 29 solutions for the 30-ply laminates.

Valot and Vannucci [5] presented some numerical solutions for FOL's made of 6 to 18 plies stacked anti-symmetrically. One of their solution is identical to $[(\pm\theta)_S/(\mp\theta)_S]$ previously presented by Caprino and Visconti [1].

Lee et al. [6] proposed some mathematical sufficient conditions for analytically obtaining FOL's. They studied a number of specially chosen anti-symmetric stacking sequences in which all coupling stiffnesses including B_{16} and B_{26} become rigorously zero. They also presented a systematic way to insert fully orthotropic cores with arbitrary thicknesses and arbitrary elastic constants between plies to provide additional FOL's.

Lee et al. [7] confirmed the five independent FIL's of for the 18 ply-laminates proposed by Vannucci and Verchery [4], and found that the number of the independent FIL's for the 27 ply-laminates are at least 340 (actually 355) instead of 219. This discrepancy is due to the fact that the 219 FIL's proposed by Vannucci & Verchery [4] are based on some sufficient conditions.

In the present study, the relatively simple analytical method proposed by Lee et al. [7] is to be extended to obtain the entire FIL solutions of (0°, +45°, -45°, 90°) layers with up to 24 plies.

2 Mathematical Modeling

Let's consider the laminates made of $(0^\circ, +45^\circ, -45^\circ, 90^\circ)$ layers with m plies for each fiber orientation, where m is a natural number no greater than 6. In order to obtain FOL's initially, some plies must be shuffled properly so that $A_{16}=A_{26}=0$, $D_{16}=D_{26}=0$ and $B_{ij}=0$ as mentioned earlier. The stiffness components, A_{ij} , B_{ij} , and D_{ij} are calculated from

$$A_{ij} = \int Q_{ij} dz, \quad (3a)$$

$$B_{ij} = \int Q_{ij} z dz, \quad (3b)$$

$$D_{ij} = \int Q_{ij} z^2 dz, \quad (3c)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} Q_{11} &= U_1 + U_2 \cos 2\theta + U_3 \cos 4\theta \\ Q_{22} &= U_1 - U_2 \cos 2\theta + U_3 \cos 4\theta \\ Q_{12} &= U_4 - U_3 \cos 4\theta \\ Q_{16} &= (U_2 \sin 2\theta) / 2 + U_3 \sin 4\theta, \\ Q_{26} &= (U_2 \sin 2\theta) / 2 - U_3 \sin 4\theta, \\ Q_{66} &= U_5 - U_3 \cos 4\theta \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} U_1 &= (3Q_{xx} + 3Q_{yy} + 2Q_{xy} + 4Q_{ss}) / 8, \\ U_2 &= (Q_{xx} - Q_{yy}) / 2, \\ U_3 &= (Q_{xx} + Q_{yy} - 2Q_{xy} - 4Q_{ss}) / 8, \\ U_4 &= (Q_{xx} + Q_{yy} + 6Q_{xy} - 4Q_{ss}) / 8, \\ U_5 &= (Q_{xx} + Q_{yy} - 2Q_{xy} + 4Q_{ss}) / 8 \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

The coordinates for the entire laminate and each ply are defined in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Laminate and ply coordinates

2.1 $(0^\circ, +45^\circ, -45^\circ, 90^\circ)_{m=3}$ stacking sequence

As an example, let's consider the $(0^\circ, +45^\circ, -45^\circ, 90^\circ)_{m=3}$ stacking sequence shown in Table 1 in which the algebraic manipulation becomes much simpler with $[(k-6)^2 - (k-6-1)^2]$ and $[(k-6)^3 - (k-6-1)^3 - 1] / 6 - 1/6$ instead of $[(k-6)^2 - (k-6-1)^2] / 2$ and $[(k-6)^3 - (k-6-1)^3] / 3$ in Eq. (3), respectively.

k	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
α	-11	-9	-7	-5	-3	-1	1	3	5	7	9	11
β	15	10	6	3	1	0	0	1	3	6	10	15
$\alpha = [(k-6)^2 - (k-6-1)^2], \beta = [(k-6)^3 - (k-6-1)^3] / 6 - 1/6$												

In order to make $D_{16}=D_{26}=0$ and D_{ij} invariant with respect to the in-plane tensor transformation, the 12 boxes on the third row, β , of Table 1 must be divided into 4 groups so that each group occupies three boxes and the numbers in each group are summed to an identical integer value. Since the total sum of the third row, 70, is not a multiple of 4, no FIL solution exists for the $(0^\circ, +45^\circ, -45^\circ, 90^\circ)_{m=3}$ laminates.

2.2 $(0^\circ, +45^\circ, -45^\circ, 90^\circ)_{m=4}$ stacking sequences

For the $(0^\circ, +45^\circ, -45^\circ, 90^\circ)_{m=4}$ stacking sequence shown in Table 2, the same strategy for α and β is unitized for simplifying the algebraic manipulation related to Eq. (3). Unlike to the previous case, the 16 numbers occupying the third row, β , of Table 2 are summed to 168 which is a multiple of 4. In order to make $D_{16}=D_{26}=0$ and D_{ij} invariant with respect to the in-plane tensor transformation, those 16 numbers must be divided into 4 groups so that each group occupies 3 boxes and the numbers in each group are summed to 42 which is a quarter of the total sum, 168. The only combination groups satisfying this summation constraint are two $(28+10+3+1)$'s and two $(21+15+6+0)$'s.

k	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
α	-15	-13	-11	-9	-7	-5	-3	-1	1	3	5	7	9	11	13	15
β	28	21	15	10	6	3	1	0	0	1	3	6	10	15	21	28
$\alpha = [(k-8)^2 - (k-8-1)^2], \beta = [(k-8)^3 - (k-8-1)^3] / 6 - 1/6$																

In addition, the numbers occupying the second row, α , for each combination group must be summed to 0, individually. However, this additional constraint can never be satisfied resulting in no FIL solution for the $(0^\circ, +45^\circ, -45^\circ, 90^\circ)_{m=4}$ laminates.

2.3 $(0^\circ, +45^\circ, -45^\circ, 90^\circ)_{m=5}$ stacking sequence

For the $(0^\circ, +45^\circ, -45^\circ, 90^\circ)_{m=5}$ stacking sequence shown in Table 3, the same strategy for α and β is unitized again. The 20 numbers occupying the third

row, β , are summed to 330 which is not a multiple of 4. Thus, there is no FIL solution for the $(0^\circ, +45^\circ, -45^\circ, 90^\circ)_{m=5}$ laminates.

k	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
a	-19	-17	-15	-13	-11	-9	-7	-5	-3	-1	1	3	5	7	9	11	13	15	17	19
β	45	36	28	21	15	10	6	3	1	0	0	1	3	6	10	15	21	28	36	45
$\alpha = [(k-10)^2 - (k-10-1)^2], \beta = [(k-10)^3 - (k-10-1)^3]/6 - 1/6$																				

2.4 $(0^\circ, +45^\circ, -45^\circ, 90^\circ)_{m=6}$ stacking sequence

For the $(0^\circ, +45^\circ, -45^\circ, 90^\circ)_{m=6}$ stacking sequence shown in Table 4, the same strategy for α and β is unitized as before. In order to make $D_{16}=D_{26}=0$ and D_{ij} , those 24 numbers occupying the third row, β , must be divided into 4 groups so that each group occupies 6 boxes and the numbers in each group are summed to 143 which is a quarter of the total sum, 572. At the same time, the numbers occupying the second row, α , for each combination group must be summed to 0, individually.

k	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24
α	-23	-21	-19	-17	-15	-13	-11	-9	-7	-5	-3	-1	1	3	5	7	9	11	13	15	17	19	21	23
β	66	55	45	36	28	21	15	10	6	3	1	0	0	1	3	6	10	15	21	28	36	45	55	66
$\alpha = [(k-12)^2 - (k-12-1)^2], \beta = [(k-12)^3 - (k-12-1)^3]/6 - (1/6)$																								

The algebraic requirement described above can be represented by the following equation.

$$\sum_{LHS} (\beta, \alpha) + \sum_{RHS} (\beta, \alpha) = (143, 0) \quad (6)$$

As an example, let's select $k=4, 7, 8, 14, 18, 24$ as shown in Table 5.

k	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24
a	-23	-21	-19	-17	-15	-13	-11	-9	-7	-5	-3	-1	1	3	5	7	9	11	13	15	17	19	21	23
β	66	55	45	36	28	21	15	10	6	3	1	0	0	1	3	6	10	15	21	28	36	45	55	66
I-1				○			○	○						○			○							○

Substituting the corresponding β 's and α 's into eq. (6) yields,

$$\sum_{LHS} (36+15+10, -17-11-9) + \sum_{RHS} (1+15+66, 3+11+23) = (143, 0) \quad (7)$$

which satisfies the algebraic requirement. Thus $k=4, 7, 8, 14, 18, 24$ can be considered as a candidate

building block for a certain fiber orientation group to construct a quarter of the FIL's.

Another example is to select $k=2, 5, 13, 15, 19, 21$ which also satisfies the algebraic requirement for the β 's and α 's as shown below.

$$\sum_{LHS} (55+28, -21-15) + \sum_{RHS} (0+3+21+36, 1+5+13+17) = (143, 0) \quad (8)$$

Likewise, all the candidate building blocks for a certain fiber orientation group listed in Table 6 can be obtained for constructing quarters of the FIL's with $(0^\circ, +45^\circ, -45^\circ, 90^\circ)_{m=6}$ stacking sequences.

k	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24
a	-23	-21	-19	-17	-15	-13	-11	-9	-7	-5	-3	-1	1	3	5	7	9	11	13	15	17	19	21	23
β	66	55	45	36	28	21	15	10	6	3	1	0	0	1	3	6	10	15	21	28	36	45	55	66
I-1				○			○	○						○			○							○
I-2/I-1	○						○			○						○	○		○		○			
I-3/I-10	○								○	○		○						○						○
I-4 ₁			○		○					○				○			○			○				○
I-4 ₂			○		○					○				○			○			○				○
I-5	○								○	○				○		○		○		○				○
I-6 ₁		○				○								○		○			○				○	
I-6 ₂			○		○					○								○		○		○		
I-6 ₃			○		○					○								○		○		○		
I-6 ₄			○		○					○								○		○		○		
I-7 ₁ /I-6 ₁		○				○						○		○					○			○		○
I-7 ₂ /I-6 ₂			○		○					○						○				○		○		○
I-7 ₃ /I-6 ₃			○		○					○						○				○		○		○
I-7 ₄ /I-6 ₄		○				○							○						○				○	
I-8/I-5		○							○							○		○						○
I-9 ₁ /I-4 ₁		○				○				○				○					○			○		○
I-9 ₂ /I-4 ₂			○		○					○									○		○		○	
I-10		○							○				○		○		○		○		○			○
II-3		○							○				○						○		○			○
II-4	○								○										○		○			○
II-9/II-4									○	○		○								○				○
II-10/II-3									○				○							○				○
$\alpha = [(k-12)^2 - (k-12-1)^2], \beta = [(k-12)^3 - (k-12-1)^3]/6 - (1/6),$ / = 'mirror image of'																								

By combining the six-number building blocks listed in Table 6, we can construct all FIL solutions with $(0^\circ, +45^\circ, -45^\circ, 90^\circ)_{m=6}$ stacking sequences. It should be noticed that some building blocks such as I-2 and I-3 are mirror images of I-1 and I-10, respectively. In the building blocks designated by type I, three numbers are selected from the LHS and the remaining three are selected from the RHS. In the building blocks designated by type II, two numbers are selected from one side and the remaining four are selected from the other side.

The next step is to select four building blocks from Table 6 so that each of the 24 boxes is occupied just once by a certain fiber orientation. After rather involved but straightforward algebraic manipulation, it can be shown that the combination with $(I-3/I-10, I-6_2/I-7_2)$ shown in Table 7 is the only possible combination for the FIL stacking sequence.

k	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24
α	-23	-21	-19	-17	-15	-13	-11	-9	-7	-5	-3	-1	1	3	5	7	9	11	13	15	17	19	21	23
β	66	55	45	36	28	21	15	10	6	3	1	0	0	1	3	6	10	15	21	28	36	45	55	66
g	1	2	3	4	3	4	2	4	1	3	1	2	1	2	4	2	3	1	3	4	3	4	1	2
$\alpha = [(k-12)^2 - (k-12-1)^2], \beta = [(k-12)^3 - (k-12-1)^3]/6 - (1/6)$																								

Even though the group numbers, g 's, in the fourth row in Table 7 are uniquely determined, the number of independent FIL stacking sequence is not one but three. This is due to the fact that once a certain fiber orientation, i.g. 0° , is assigned to a specific group number, $g=1$ for $k=1$ in Table 7, the fiber orientation in the adjacent ply with $g=2$ can be one of $+45^\circ, -45^\circ$, or 90° . Once we fix the location of 0° to group 1, we have only three choices for allocating 90° plies to one of the remaining three groups 2, 3, and 4. If we treat any horizontal or vertical mirror image of a certain stacking sequence is dependent solution, we can allocate the remaining two groups to $\pm 45^\circ$ plies arbitrarily. Thus we have only three independent FIL's for the laminates made of $(0^\circ, +45^\circ, -45^\circ, 90^\circ)$ plies with up to 24 plies. Table 8 shows the three independent FIL's and one of them is identical to the result of Vannucci & Verchery [4]

0/9/+/-/+/-/9/-/0/+0/9 0/9/-/9/+0/+/-/+/-/0/9
-/9/+0/+0/9/0/-/+/-/9 -/9/0/9/+/-/+0/+0/-/9
+/9/0/-/0/-/9/-/+0/+9 +/9/-/9/0/+0/-/0/-/+9

3 Concluding Remarks

In contrast to the one independent FIL's of $(0^\circ, +45^\circ, -45^\circ, 90^\circ)_{m=6}$ stacking sequence found by Vannucci and Verchery [4], three FIL solutions are obtained by the present study.

The present method will be further generalized to obtain independent FIL stacking sequences made of

$(0^\circ, +72^\circ, -72^\circ, +144^\circ, -144^\circ)$ layers with up to 30 plies.

Acknowledgements

The present study has been supported by the Ministry of Knowledge Economy, the Republic of Korea, under KHP Dual-Use Component Development Program.

References

- [1] G. Caprino, and Crivelli Visconti I. "A Note on Specially Orthotropic Laminates", *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 16, pp 395~399. Sept. 1982.
- [2] J. W. Gunnink Comments on "A Note on Specially Orthotropic Laminates", *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 17, pp 508~510, Nov. 1983.
- [3] J. Lee, J. Kim, and Y. Choi, "Analysis of Specially Anti-Symmetric Stacking Sequences with Pascal's Triangle and Pythagorean Theorem", *2002 Spring Conference, The Korean Society for Aeronautical and Space Science*, 2002.
- [4] Vannucci P., and Verchery G., "A New Method for Generating Fully Isotropic Laminates", *Composite Structures*, Vol. 58, pp 75~82, 2002.
- [5] Valot E., and Vannucci P., "Some Exact Solutions for Fully Orthotropic Laminates", *Composite Structures*, Vol. 69, pp 157~166, 2005.
- [6] J. Lee, J. Kim, and H. Kim, "Analytical Laminate Stacking Sequences for Perfect Orthotropy", 6th Asian-Pacific Conference on Aerospace Technology and Science (APCATS 2009), , Huangshan, China, Nov. 2009.
- [7] J. Lee, J. Kim, and H. Kim, "Fully isotropic laminates with up to twenty seven plies", 27th International Congress of the Aeronautical Sciences, Nice, France, Sep. 2010.